

Supplementary material

Focus group guide to co-evaluate the experience in the Didascalía-Virtual-Classroom Immersive Virtual Reality (IVRE) environment

Organization

Two roles are selected:

- (1) Moderator who will act as facilitator.
- (2) Support for time control and audio recording.

It is recommended to record the discussion to speed up the dynamics and to have an accurate record of the debate. It is recommended that a test be made with the cell phone recorder to verify that it is working properly and to check the state of the battery. During the discussion they should check from time to time that it is working properly and that the recording is being made. In case of poor audio or no recording, it is difficult to retrieve the information.

The person who assumes the role of facilitator should highlight the importance of having spontaneous opinions from the participants, conveying to them that it is not a matter of evaluating their answers, whether they are right or wrong. The discussion should take place in a relaxed atmosphere, offering the participants a space for reflection and even the possibility of expanding on a particular topic, or making a comment/suggestion on the actions and issues assessed.

Guidelines for developing the Discussion Group

I.- Experience (about 10'). The person who has done the internship in the ERVI explains his experience

- a) Regarding the tool: general sensations.
- b) Regarding the teaching methodology: How did you decide to start the session?
- c) Regarding the conflicts: Which ones did you detect? How did you feel (emotional experience, affective states, first reaction, self-control...)?
- d) What did you think about during the pause between one scenario and the other and what did you decide to do to manage and/or resolve the conflicts?
- e) What do you think about the feedback received by the system?

II. Strategies (about 15'). Co-reflection on communication strategies for classroom conflict management.

Based on the observations undertaken, participants share their reflections regarding the performance and offer feedback on the strategies used by the person who conducted the ERVI experience in three different scenarios/cases:

- (a) Which ones have been most useful?
- b) Which ones helped to avoid conflict escalation?
- c) What could have been done differently, and why?

III. Impact (about 15'). Participants reflect on the usability and potential of the tool for initial and continuous teacher training.

- a) Potential, strengths and limitations with regard to other learning methodologies, e.g., video viewing, role playing, etc.
- b) Points to improve in order to continue developing the tool: scenarios, personages, dialogues, feedback, etc.
- c) Assessment of the possibility of the availability of this resource and its implementation in educational establishments for continuous (self-) training in strategies for conflict management and resolution.

The Focus Group will be concluded when the moderator considers that all the topics included in this guide have been discussed and that sufficient depth on the topic has been achieved. At the completion of the Focus Group, the recorded audio will be sent to the teacher.